

Assessing Apical Toxicity and Sublethal Responses of Earthworms in PFAS-Contaminated Soils: A Comprehensive Study at a Fire Training Site in Sweden

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Background:

Fire training sites and airports are significant sources of PFAS contamination, primarily due to use of Aqueous Film-Forming Foam (AFFF) containing PFAS. Despite recent global policies restricting higher-than-C8 PFAS congeners, the persistent legacy of PFOS and PFOA continues to impact aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Contemporary AFFF formulations often include short-chain PFAS and their oxidizable fluoroalkylamine precursors. Terrestrial ecosystems, crucial for vital services, are under threat. Earthworms, acting as essential bioindicators, play a key role in soil processes and ecosystem services. This study aims to comprehensively assess the impact of PFAS-contaminated AFFF on earthworms, emphasizing the need for sustainable policies to control PFAS contamination.

Aim of work:

This study aims to comprehensively assess the impact of PFAS-contaminated soil on earthworms, emphasizing the need for sustainable firefighting policies. We investigated apical toxicity and sublethal responses of earthworms across a PFAS contamination gradient from a drill site in Trelleborg, Sweden (see map on the right side panel). PFAS contamination in soil was assessed by target LC-MS/MS analysis (sum of 22), ranging from 960 ppb (B1) to 7 ppb (B7). OECD acute and chronic tests -plus a suite of sublethal assessments after 30 days incubation in soil- were conducted. Biomarkers included immune-related responses, enzymatic activities, and a behavioral test (escape). Pristine garden soil served as an external reference control.

Work Plan:

The apical toxicity and sublethal responses of earthworms across a PFAS contamination gradient from a drill site in Trelleborg, Sweden (see map on the right side panel) was assessed. OECD No. 222 test (reproduction), alongside sublethal effect assessments after 30 days of exposure where carried out analyzing several biomarkers encompassing cellular, tissutal, and behavioral indicators, such as oxidative burst, enzymatic responses (phenol oxidase, catalase, acetylcholinesterase), and an escape test. Standard OECD soil, with PFAS levels below the limit of detection, where used as a control. In contaminated soils PFAS analysis -sum of 22- was carried out according to US EPA draft Method 1633 using LC-MS and isotopic labelled standards.

Trelleborg demonstrational site map

Table 1) PFAS concentration in sampled soil.

Top Soil	B1	B4	B5	B6	B7
Sum of PFOA, PFOS, PFNA, PFHxS (ppb)	910	8	23	7	5
Sum of 22 PFAS (ppb)	960	11	33	10	7

Results:

1^ Tier of investigation: Molecular effects

2^ Tier of investigation: Enzymatic effects

3^ Tier of investigation: Neurotoxic effects

4^ Tier of investigation: Ecological effects

Figure 1A) & 1B) Real time Quantitative PCR was carried to assess the relative expression of two genes involved in immune response, i.e. Lysenin and Celomic Cytolytic Factor 1 (CCF-1). Data on B7 are still ongoing. All data was analysed using the $\Delta\Delta Cq$ method using 18S as a reference gene. The statistical significance was evaluated using Welch's ANOVA test using with GraphPad Prism 9.

Figure 2) Catalase activity was assessed through an in-gel zymographic assay after native PAGE in SN10 obtained from *E. foetida* whole tissue extracts (n=20). Data represent average +/- SEM.

Figure 3) Phenol oxidase enzyme activity was assessed in whole earthworm tissue lysate (SN10, 1 μ g of protein), shed light on potential immuno-toxic effects (n=20).

All data were analyzed with GraphPad Prism 9 using Welch's ANOVA test.

Figure 4) Acetylcholinesterase activity assessed by the Ellman's assay using acetylthiocholine as a substrate (Ickus.com) in order to evaluate the potential neurotoxic effect of long-term exposure to PFAS (n=20). All data were analyzed with GraphPad Prism 9 using Welch's ANOVA test. Data represent average +/- SEM.

Figure 5) Behavioral test was performed by assessing the ability of every single tested specimen to escape a stressful situation (200 mM NaCl) (n=20). All data were analyzed with GraphPad Prism 9 using Welch's ANOVA test.

Figure 6) Biomass of earthworm specimens was measured after 30 day of exposure to compare the difference between reference control and the PFAS gradient sites.

Figure 7) & 8) Mortality test was carried out at two different time points (7 days and 14 days) whereas the reproduction test was carried out after 30 days by counting cocoons found inside the soil. These tests are OECD standard No. 207 and 222, respectively.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, our study provides a comprehensive body of evidence aligning with the current understanding of PFAS toxicity, indicating that while these compounds may not exhibit high acute toxicity, they have the potential to disrupt various biological processes in terrestrial organisms over the long term. Utilizing a multi-tiered approach, we aimed to investigate and illustrate the effects of prolonged exposure to PFAS. Our experiments with *E. foetida*, a pivotal species in soil ecosystems, yielded intriguing results spanning from molecular to ecological perspectives. The correlation observed between bioassay results and biomarkers suggests a consistent trend across a contamination gradient of 7 to 33 ppb PFAS22 (sum of 22 congeners), predicting higher-order effects. These findings underscore the concern surrounding PFAS contamination, even at relatively low concentrations. Future investigations should encompass a comprehensive analysis of total PFAS using standardized approaches such as TOP, TOF, and AOF methodologies.

Relevant references:

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